

Guidelines for the Annotation of ExtrART: Evaluation Dataset for Entity Extraction from *The Lives Of The Artists* (1550)

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Introduction: Entity Extraction is a fundamental task for Art-historical texts, due to their potential to enrich already available Knowledge Bases. However, if entities extracted by Entity Extraction tools are often defined via proper names or phrasal constituents which have a *referential* rather than *descriptive* nature (e.g., proper names), artifacts, which are described in these texts, are complex objects which are more often referenced using several attributes which have distinct linguistic features (materials, motifs, dates, etc.).

Task 1: Entity and Concept Recognition

This task consists in identifying in-text references to entities which are related to the history of arts and artifacts. For the sake of clarity, we distinguish 4 layers: Named entities, generic concepts, iconography and time expressions. Each layer considers different annotation strategies to define the information to extract.

1. Classes and definitions

Class	Layer	Description	Example
Person (PER)	Named Entity	Humans and fictional characters	Verrocchio, Leonardo, Donatello, Michelangelo
Organization (ORG)	Named Entity	Organizations, political and religious groups	Family of the Medici, Congregation of Camaldoli
Location (LOC)	Named Entity	Natural places, buildings and facilities	Palazzo Vecchio, Florence, Milan
Miscellaneous (MISC)	Named Entity	Miscellaneous entities, such as cultural products, historical events, etc	siege of Florence, Carnival, Old Testament
Artwork (WORK)	Named Entity	Titled human creations which have a primarily aesthetic purpose, such as statues, monuments or paintings	Pieta of Michelangelo, David of Donatello
Object (OBJ)	Generic	Result of human activity which is considered creative and requires effort or labor.	work of art, copy, picture, book
Visual Work (OBJvis)	Generic	Subclass of creative objects which are primarily	statue, scene, depiction, figure,

		perceived by the sense of sight.	model
Built Work (OBJarch)	Generic	Generic buildings, man-made environments and related components	Church, house, building, arch, roof, altar
Material (MAT)	Generic	Material from which artifacts are composed.	marble, oil, wood, soil, glass.
Technique (TECH)	Generic	Techniques from which works are made.	Fresco, low-relief, plating
Represented subject (SUBJ)	Iconography	objects, entities, themes and motifs depicted in a work, which can occur in its title or in an ekphrasis	S. Peter, nude David, head, book, Adoration of the Magi, grotesque
State of represented (STATE)	Iconography	Phrasal constituents which predicate specific attributes of the represented.	[Mary] _{rep} [standing with many angels above her] _{state}
Time (DATE)	Time expression	Expressions which refer either to one specific date, a duration or a date interval.	in 1984, between 1250 and 1253, after the death of Cosimo, in the next year

2. Lexical characteristics of annotation layers

Generic concepts: Artifacts, Material, Technique

Usually terms referring to generic concepts are expressed with common nouns, more rarely with noun phrases (*silver plating*, *Corinthian order*). For this layer, the annotation considers just the lexical units which occur in fine-art thesauri. This means that adjectives or numerals which express additional information are left unannotated.

- Giovanni of Pisa designed the <OBJarch>façade<OBJarch> of the <OBJarch>Duomo<OBJarch> with three principal <OBJarch>doors<OBJarch>.

Named entities: Person, Location, Artworks, Organization, Miscellaneous

These entities usually consist of proper names, rarely of noun phrases (*School of Athens*, *Nuns of S. Jacopo*, *house of Medici*). Named entities may contain toponyms (*Leonardo da Vinci*), patronymics (*Michelangelo di Lodovico di Buonarroti*), epithets and temporal roles (*Ser Brunelleschi*, *King Julius*) and appositives (*Antonino, Archbishop of Florence*).

Artworks are further special cases. Their titles are usually identifiable by the presence of double-quotes, capitalized words or definite articles. Even though these references may or may not be capitalized, it's important that they unambiguously refer to a piece of work.

Nested entities with a limit of depth 1. Nested Entities are annotated with a greedy approach, i.e. the maximum number of nested entities should be annotated.

- <PER>Pope Leo</PER> commissioned the <LOC><OBJarch>Chamber</OBJarch> of <PER>Our Lady</PER> at <LOC>Loreto</LOC></LOC> to <PER>Maestro Andrea Contucci of <LOC>Monte Sansovino</LOC></PER>.
- This is stated in his <OBJ>book</OBJ> <MISC>“De Asse”</MISC> and in his <OBJ>observations</OBJ> on the <MISC>Pandects</MISC>.
- a <OBJ>copy</OBJ> of the <OBJvis>picture</OBJvis> in which <PER>Raffaello</PER> had formerly painted <WORK>portraits of <PER>Pope Leo X</PER>, <PER>Cardinal Giulio de’ Medici</PER> and <PER>Cardinal de’ Rossi</PER></WORK>.

Iconography: Represented and State of Represented

These categories are used to define iconographic subjects. Represented entities are usually referenced via common or proper nouns. States of represented are usually verb phrases which depict the state in which the represented is usually depicted. While the annotation of represented entities follows the same rules of generic concepts and named entities, state of represented may include long phrasal structures whose only boundary is the proposition end.

- He depicted <represented₁>Our Lady</represented₁> <state_of_represented₁>standing, raised from the <represented₂>ground</represented₂> on a <represented₃>pedestal</represented₃>, and uplifting her <represented₄>head</represented₄> towards <represented₅>Heaven</represented₅></state_of_represented₁>.

Task 2. Resolution using Controlled Vocabularies and Knowledge Graphs

In order to add semantics to the terms and entities extracted in T1, these should be mapped to unique entries in a thesaurus or Knowledge Graph. In specific:

- **Generic concepts** (Artifacts, Visual Works, Built Works, Materials and Techniques) should be mapped to the respective terms in the AAT hierarchy. For example the term “church” is mapped to the entry <churches (buildings), 300007466>.
- **Named entities** (Persons, Organizations, Location, Artworks and Miscellaneous) are linked to entries in Wikidata, which acts as a general-purpose encyclopedia.
- **Iconography terms** which define represented entities and their states are described using Iconclass notations. For example in “David holding the head of Goliath”, “nude David” is resolved to the Iconclass notation <11I62(DAVID), David (not in biblical context)> while the state “holding the head of Goliath” is resolved to <71H145, David with Goliath’s head>.

The only layer which does not consider a resolution step is the Time Expression layer. In each other layer, if a sequence cannot be linked to any term in the considered thesaurus or KB, the default null value is `NIL`.

Special cases

a. Multiple true links for a single surface form: In some cases, more than one link can be possible for the same surface form. This is especially true for artworks which have the same title as their depicted theme, as in *Ecce Homo*. In this case, two overlapping annotations are provided, one for the subject (MISC) and one for the artwork (WORK), with two different KB identifiers.

b. Ambiguous Named Entities: Since we are dealing with excerpts from books, often historical persons can be referenced only with their first name, since the original full name may be given in other parts of the book or is implicit. This causes a certain ambiguity which often requires the annotator to take in consideration the context to understand what is the correct link for a surface form. In this case, we decided to annotate first names too, however we decided to not penalize a model which is not capable of disambiguating them correctly by labeling them both as `NIL` and with a corresponding Wikidata identifier, if available.

The same situation occurs for capitalized words in Vasari's book which do not refer to a specific individual or entity, such as "Pope", "Saint", "King", etc. For these entities, we decided to provide two possible links:

- a *very* specific link, disambiguating the entity with the specific individual which is mentioned
- an *appropriate* link, which is not the entity truly mentioned by the author but rather represents the concept conveyed by the word.

Example:

- The Sistine Chapel was commissioned by the [Pope]_{Pope Sixtus IV, Pope}